

Supplementary data

Supplementary files: Output files produced by *ReplicaTE* on the two species *D. melanogaster* and *A. thaliana*.

Figure S1: Recall metrics for *D. melanogaster* and *A. thaliana* for the three read coverages for the reference insertions according to the different precision localization tested.

Figure S2: Precision metrics for *D. melanogaster* and *A. thaliana* for the three read coverages for the reference insertions according to the different precision localization tested.

Figure S3: *Fscore* metrics for *D. melanogaster* and *A. thaliana* for the three read coverages for the reference insertions according to the different precision localization tested.

Figure S4: Recall metrics for *D. melanogaster* and *A. thaliana* for the three read coverages for the non-reference insertions according to the different precision localization tested.

Figure S5: Precision metrics for *D. melanogaster* and *A. thaliana* for the three read coverages for the non-reference insertions according to the different precision localization tested.

Figure S6: *Fscore* metrics for *D. melanogaster* and *A. thaliana* for the three read coverages for the non-reference insertions according to the different precision localization tested.

Figure S7: Recall and precision metrics of the different tested programs on *Bos taurus* simulated data.

Figure S8: Impact of the structure of the ERV input consensus sequences (panel A) and ERV families (panel B) on recall and precision metrics using TEFLoN on *Bos taurus* simulated data.

The detection of reference insertions is represented with circles and the detection of non-reference insertions with triangles.

Figure S9: Performance of TEFLoN and impact of read coverage in the detection of ERV insertions in 10 *Bos taurus* samples. A) Recall and precision metrics, B) Number of TP and FP according to the short-read depth sequencing. Depth was computed on trimmed reads mapped on the cattle reference genome.

Supplementary Table S1: Accession numbers of 10 WGS short-read data samples of *Bos taurus*.

Supplementary file 1: command lines used to run Jitterbug and TEPID.

Supplementary file 2: command lines for the pre-processing of long and short read data.

Supplementary file 3: TE annotations for *B. taurus*.